

ISic0806

Epitaph of Alliena

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

volcanic (pietra di Fuardo)

Object

stele

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Lipara

Place of origin (modern)

Lipari

Provenance

Exact provenance unknown, first noted in the Palermo Archaeological Museum

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Lipari, Museo Archeologico

Regionale Eoliano "Luigi Bernabò Brea", inventory 12331

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height 107 cm

Width 36.5 cm

Depth 10 cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1-4: 50-60 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: not recorded mm

Text

1. Ἀλλιήν

2. ας

3. Δωροθέ

4. ας

Apparatus

Text of I.Lipara

Libertini: Ἀδαίηνας

Translation (en)

(tomb of) Alliena Dorothea

Commentary

For the name Alliena/us (attested several times at Lipara), note A. Allienus [<http://romanrepublic.ac.uk/person/2324>] , legatus of Q. Cicero in Asia in 60, was governor of Sicily 48-46 BC. Dorothea [<http://www.lgpn.ox.ac.uk/id/>

V3a-38315] is not otherwise attested in Sicily.

Digital identifiers:

TM 644903

PHI 334765

Bibliography

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